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Use of CFD in the design of heat exchangers

Fluid Mechanics

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Use of CFD in the design of heat exchangers

Astract:

This report indicates a cost-saving alternative to trial and error practices and allows designers to explore "what if" scenarios in the analysis and deigning for heat and mass transfer through heat exchanger by help of different engineering software like Solidworks, Ansys (engineering simulation and 3D design software) and MATLAB. For this purpose, in this research paper we created designs for a radiator heat exchanger in steps (i.e., Singular tube, with different shapes of fins, without headers and with headers).

Introduction:

A heat exchanger is a device that facilitates the transfer of energy between one or more fluid streams with an existing temperature difference. It is type of system that is used to transfer heat between two or more fluids. In both the processes like heating and cooling the heat exchangers are used. To prevent the mixing of the fluids a solid wall is used that keeps the fluids from being directly in contact. Heat exchangers are a key component of industry and play a critical role in the smooth running of industry [1]. Many engineering applications rely on heat transfer e.g.:

Figure 1 HVAC System

Figure 2 Radiator

Figure 3 Hydel Generator Surface Air Coolers

Figure 4 Industrial heat exchanger

Heat Exchanger Flow Configurations:

Heat exchangers have three primary flow configurations: [2]

Parallel flow – the two fluids enter at the same end of the heat exchanger and flow in the same direction, parallel to one another. In this design, the temperature differences are large at the inlet, but the fluid temperatures will approach a similar value at the outlets.

Counter flow – the two fluids enter at opposite ends of the heat exchanger and flow counter to one another. In this design, the temperature differences are less but more constant over the length of the exchanger. It is possible that the fluid being heated may leave the exchanger at a higher temperature than the exit temperature of the heating fluid [3]. This is the most efficient design because of higher temperature differential over length of the exchanger [4].

Cross flow – the two fluids flow perpendicular to one another.

There can be more than one method of heat transfer in a heat exchanger. Heat transfer will occur using one or more modes of transfer, conduction, convection, or radiation [5].

The CFD analysis numerical measurements and algorithms are used to study the flow of fluids through objects. The object and fluid are divided into finite elements or cells, each of which has finite dimensions. For each cell, the mass, momentum and energy are calculated and outcome of the calculation for one cell is the input for the calculation for the next cell. The smaller the dimensions of the cells, the more calculations are performed and the more accurate the result. In short, CFD allows us to perform numerical experiments in a virtual flow laboratory on a computer [6].

Literature Review:

Computational Fluid Dynamics in Heat Exchanger Design and Analysis:

A customer approached that had several condensers installed which were giving performance problems. The condensers simply did not perform to their capacity. The suspicion was that the distribution or flow over the inner tubes can lead to performance issues [7].

Approaching the Problem:

First, the heat exchanger with its inlet header was redesigned using 3D CAD software. The process fluid was analyzed to obtain its physical properties, and, using a flow simulation software package with the CAD software, the behavior of the fluid in the heat exchanger was calculated.

Figure 5

An Improved Solution to the Problem:

The question that comes next is: What can be done to improve the flow of the product through the heat exchanger? How can we create an even distribution of product across all the heat exchanger tubes?

Further CFD analysis was performed on the same inlet header but this time with concentric reducers fitted in the flow path. The aim was to test if the reducer design would be able to divert fluid towards the outer ring of tubes and improve the flow distribution.

This case study shows how CFD is a very powerful tool for checking hypotheses about fluid behaviors. It also allows the design engineer to analyse prototypes inside a virtual laboratory before money is spent on prototypes and manufacturing. As you can see, using the latest Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) technologies provides savings in time and money which we are able to pass on to our customers.

Figure 6

Governing equations in Ansys

Most of the equations, parameters and models to be discussed in this section are adapted from different CFD studies of shell and tube heat exchangers. For the governing equations, the time dependent terms of the conservation of mass, momentum (x, y, and z planes) and energy are dropped for the steady-state analysis of the STHE, as shown in Eqs. (1) to (6). The conservation of energy equation accounts for a dissipation function (Φ). Note that all of the equations presented in this section are built-in functions of the ANSYS CFX solver for running the simulations. [5]

$$\nabla(\rho\bar{V}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla(\rho u\bar{V}) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}}{\partial z} \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla(\rho v\bar{V}) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zy}}{\partial z} + \rho g \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla(\rho w\bar{V}) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla(\rho e\bar{V}) = -p\nabla(\bar{V}) + \nabla(k\nabla T) + q + \Phi \quad (5)$$

$$\Phi = \mu \left[2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] + \lambda (\nabla \bar{V})^2 \quad (6)$$

Converting of differential equation into algebraic equation:

- Governing Differential Equation for 1-D steady state heat conduction

$$\frac{d^2 T}{dx^2} = 0 \quad \dots\dots(5)$$

- From Taylor series expansion

$$T(x+dx) = T(x) + \frac{dT}{dx} \frac{dx}{1!} + \frac{d^2 T}{dx^2} \frac{(dx)^2}{2!} + \frac{d^3 T}{dx^3} \frac{(dx)^3}{3!} + \frac{d^4 T}{dx^4} \frac{(dx)^4}{4!} + \dots\dots$$

$$+ T(x-dx) = T(x) - \frac{dT}{dx} \frac{dx}{1!} + \frac{d^2 T}{dx^2} \frac{(dx)^2}{2!} - \frac{d^3 T}{dx^3} \frac{(dx)^3}{3!} + \frac{d^4 T}{dx^4} \frac{(dx)^4}{4!} - \dots\dots$$

$$T(x+dx)+T(x-dx) = 2T(x) + \frac{d^2 T}{dx^2} (dx)^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{d^2 T}{dx^2} = \frac{T(x+dx)+T(x-dx) - 2T(x)}{(dx)^2}$$

$$\frac{T(x+dx)+T(x-dx) - 2T(x)}{(dx)^2} = 0$$

$$T(x+dx)+T(x-dx) - 2T(x) = 0$$

$$T(x) = \frac{T(x+dx)+T(x-dx)}{2}$$

$$T(i) = \frac{T(i+1)+T(i-1)}{2}$$

Background:

The fundamental basis of almost all CFD problems is the Navier–Stokes equations, which define many single-phase (gas or liquid, but not both) fluid flows. These equations can be simplified by removing terms describing viscous actions to yield the Euler equations. Further simplification, by removing terms describing vorticity yields the full potential equations.

One of the earliest type of calculations resembling modern CFD are those by Lewis Fry Richardson, in the sense that these calculations used finite differences and divided the physical space in cells. Although they failed dramatically, these calculations, together with Richardson's book *Weather Prediction by Numerical Process* [8], set the basis for modern CFD and numerical meteorology. In fact, early CFD calculations during the 1940s using ENIAC used methods close to those in Richardson's 1922 book [9].

Thermotical Background:

Stages of a CFD Analysis

- Pre-processing: (problem formulation (geometry, equations, boundary conditions), computational mesh)
- Solving: (discretization, solving)
- Post-processing: (analysis, visualization)

Discretisation methods:

The stability of the selected discretisation is generally established numerically rather than analytically as with simple linear problems. Special care must also be taken to ensure that the

discretization handles discontinuous solutions gracefully. The Euler equations and Navier–Stokes equations both admit shocks, and contact surfaces. [10]

Some of the discretization methods being used are:

- Finite-difference: – discretise differential equations

$$0 = \frac{\delta u}{\delta x} + \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta y} \approx \frac{u_{i+1,j} - u_{i-1,j}}{2\Delta x} - \frac{v_{i,j+1} - v_{i,j-1}}{2\Delta x}$$

Figure 4

- Finite-volume: – discretise control-volume equations

$$0 = \text{net mass outflow} = (\rho u A)_e - (\rho u A)_w + n(\rho v A)_n - (\rho v A)_s$$

- Finite-element: – represent solution as a weighted sum of basic functions

Figure 5

$$u(x) = \left(\sum u \alpha S \alpha x \right)$$

Simulation:

Singular tube:

Rectangular Fin:

First we analyze a heatexhanger with an extended reactangular surface (fin).Its sink temperature is taken as 90 centigrate. While surrounding is taken as 25 centigrate.

Figure 4

Figure 5

Numerical Analysis of 1-D Conduction Steady state heat transfer with MATLAB:

Then simulate a simple 1D steady state equation for

For $i=1$:

$$T=T_b$$

For $i = 2 \leq i \leq (N-1)$

$$T(i) = \frac{T(i+1) + T(i-1)}{2}$$

For $i=N$

$$T(N) = T(N-1)$$

```

clc
clear all
%Geometry parameter
L=100; %Length of fin
N=100; %no. of nodes
dx=L/(N-1);

T=zeros(N,1);
Tb=90; %base temp
k=100; %no. of iteratin

for j=1:1:k
    T(1,1)=Tb;
    for i=2:1:N-1
        T(i,1)=(T(i+1,1)+T(i-1,1))/2;
    end
    T(N,1)=T(N-1,1);
end
plot(T);

```


Figure 6

For Hemi Sphere:

Figure 7

Experiment:

Heated the water in boiler up to 90 centigrade. And attach it to radiator by pipe. The velocity of water is found by its flow rate.

Then taken it intend values of outlet and inlet temperature.

Figure 9 Boiler

Figure 10 Copper Radiator and its CAD Model

Experiential Values:

velocity (m/s)	Time (s)	T (inlet) (C)	T(Outlet)	Temperature Difference
0.2	1	91.5	49.5	42
0.2	2	91.5	52	39.5
0.2	3	91.5	52.7	38.8

0.2	4	91.5	53.2	38.3
0.2	5	91.5	53.8	37.7
0.2	6	91.5	54	37.5
0.2	7	91.5	54	37.5
0.2	8	91.5	54.2	37.3
0.2	9	91.5	53.8	37.7
0.2	10	91.5	54	37.5

Figure 11

Conclusion

This case study shows how CFD is a very powerful tool for checking theories about fluid behaviors. It also allows the design engineer to analyze prototypes inside a virtual laboratory before money is spent on prototypes and manufacturing. It can technologies provides savings in time, material and money. And through this software we can enhance the performance of heat exchanger too by changing scenarios.

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